

Perception Relating to Factors Affecting Marketing Tea in Tamilnadu

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Abstract

Marketing means selling of goods and services to customers. Marketing of tea by respondents is done in many methods. Because goods once produced must be sold at the earliest in order to achieve the aim of production. Delay in sales leads to lot of financial and other inconveniences to the produces. There are many channels of distribution of Tea. The various media of sales and the variables related to marketing of Tea are identified and the attitude on each component was analyzed.

Keywords: Medium Farmers, Commission Agents, Retailers

Introduction

Indians depend on Agriculture. It is the mainstay of Indian economy because of its high share in employment and livelihood creation notwithstanding its reduced contribution to the nation's GDP. The share of agriculture in the Gross Domestic Product has registered a steady decline from 36.4 per cent in 1982-83 to 18.5 per cent in 2006-2007 and increased to 22.1 per cent in 2013. Yet this sector continues to support more than half a billion people providing employment to 52 per cent of the workforce. It is also an important source of raw material and demand for many industrial products particularly fertilizers, pesticides, agricultural implements and a variety of consumer goods. Growth of agriculture over a period of time remained lower than the growth in non – agriculture sectors and this decelerating trend is a cause for concern.

As for as Agriculture sector is concerned, it needs well functioning markets to drive growth, employment, and economic prosperity in rural areas of the country. To provide dynamism and efficiency into the marketing system, large investment is required for the development of post – harvest and cold chain infrastructure nearer to the farmer's fields.

Accordingly the Ministry of Agriculture circulated a model Agriculture Produce Marketing Committee (APMC) Act, 2003 and suggested amendments to the state APMC Acts so as to promote investment in marketing infrastructure, motivated corporate sector to undertake direct marketing and facilitated a national integrated market.

Statement of the problem

Tea has occupied an important place in Indian economy for the last several decades. In fact, Tea industry is regarded as one of the most important agro based industries in India. It provides direct employment to over one million workers in the country. Unlike other agricultural crops, Tea provides the highest employment per unit of arable land. In 2002, there were 12.55 lakh people employed in Tea plantations. Women contributed about 50 per cent of the workforce. Many more are employed by other sectors related to Tea and Tea trade like Tea machinery, packing, ware houses, etc.

Tea was cultivated mainly in the northern region of India, Bengal's Darjeeling, and Dooars, Assam and Cachar. In the south, Tea was grown in Tamil Nadu and Kerala's hilly western Ghat region of the total 1998 production, 77 per cent came from northern India. Assam valley produced the highest share of 46 per cent and Dooars produced 17 per cent in the South, Nilgiris of Tamil Nadu produced 14 per cent. Over 80 per cent of Tea manufactured in India was of CTC Tea and average Orthodox Tea production was 13 per cent⁵ hard hit by depressed world prices for Tea, rubber and garments. However, recent weakness in world prices for Tea could depress export earnings⁶. Prices at the Colombo Tea auctions, which dropped sharply following the August 1998 Russian financial crisis, improved in the second half of 1999 due to increased buying by Russia and a drop in world supply. However, the annual average price in 1999 remained 14 per cent below 1998.

The demand for Tea has been on the increase the government of India has not been taking steps to promote new products of Tea. The existing produces also are facing numerous problems regarding marketing them. Many factors are also responsible for easy promotion of Tea hence a study.

Objectives

Following are the objectives of the present study.

- To study the profile of tea industry and the characteristics of the respondents.
- To study the attitude of respondents to the services of middlemen.
- To assess the perception of the respondents towards marketing Tea.

Sampling design

In social science research, a sample size of 300 to 400 is found adequate to obtain meaningful inferences and hence in the present study, the sample size is confined to 370 respondents.

Three hundred and seventy respondents covering 145 direct sales respondents, 120 respondents who sell through single agent and 105 respondents following other means of sales were selected for the study by applying Random sample technique. Tippet random sampling numbers were used and they were selected for the study.

Tools for Analysis

The analysis of the dissertation consists of three parts. The first part of the analysis is about analyzing the characteristics of the respondents. Every variable was analysed with the help of percentage to total. Compound Growth Rate (CGR) and co-efficient of variation (CV) were applied to measure the growth on selected variables.

Factors Affecting Tea Marketing

a. Marketing To Middlemen

Tea producers market their products through many channels. One among those channels is the middlemen who are part and parcel of the channel of distribution. Direct sales mean to be impossible and has many hurdles to overcome

Table 1 Attitude of Respondents towards Marketing to Middlemen

Sl. No	Perception	Means Score			F Statistics
		Direct Sales	Single Agent	Other Means	
1	Village merchants help me	2.2320	2.3340	2.1301	22.069**
2	Commission agents provide service	2.2157	2.3020	2.2649	7.4739**
3	Regulated market function properly	2.6013	2.7082	2.4944	16.0618**
4	Co-operative market society also renders	2.1637	2.2906	2.0362	0.0212NS
5	Wholesalers help me	2.2222	2.3222	2.1223	0.5994NS
6	Local traders	2.0033	2.0865	1.9200	4.2613*
7	Pre harvesting contractor	2.1144	2.2312	1.9975	2.7897*

Source: Primary data

It is observed from Table 1 that the perception of respondents of single agent was higher in all the respects of Marketing to Middlemen except two causes than that of the respondents of direct sales and other means as revealed by the respective mean scores that are higher in the selected factors. The highly perceived factors among the respondents of ‘Direct Sales’ category are Regulated market function properly, Village merchants help me and Wholesalers help me since their respective mean scores are 2.6013, 2.2320 and 2.2222 respectively. Among the ‘Single Agent’ category of respondents too these factors are Regulated market function properly, Village merchants help me and Wholesalers help me since their mean scores are 2.7082, 2.3340 and 2.3222 respectively. Among the ‘Other Means’ category of respondents, these factors are Regulated market function properly, Commission agents provide service and Village merchants help me since their mean scores are 2.4944, 2.2649 and 2.1301 respectively. With regard to all category of respondents, statements Local traders only has ranked the least with 2.0033, 2.0865 and 1.9200 mean scores respectively.

B. Preferring Commission Agents

Commission agents also play a very dominant role in selling the Tea produced by the respondents because in some study areas village merchants may not deal correctly with the respondents. But commission agents provide add on services to the respondents.

Table 2 Attitude of Respondents towards Preferring Commission Agents

Sl. No	Perception	Means Score			F Statistics
		Direct Sales	Single Agent	Other Means	
1	Immediate cash payment	2.0261	2.1135	1.9388	2.2118 NS
2	Advance received is on time	2.4412	2.5523	2.3301	2.632*
3	Transport facilities made available	2.3235	2.4260	2.2211	0.6718 NS
4	Storage facilities made available	2.5915	2.6941	2.4889	0.5582 NS
5	Long term practice is followed	2.4314	2.5374	2.3253	4.1391*
6	Higher price when compared to village merchants/regulated markets	2.2353	2.3496	2.1210	5.6801**

Source: Primary data

Table 2 shows that the perception of respondents of single agent was higher in all the respects of preferring commission agents except two causes than that of the respondents of direct sales and

other means as revealed by the respective mean scores that are higher in the selected factors. The highly perceived factors among the respondents of ‘Direct Sales’ category are Storage facilities made available, Advance received is on time and Long term practice is followed since their respective mean scores are 2.5915, 2.4412 and 2.4314 respectively. Among the ‘Single Agent’ category of respondents too these factors are Storage facilities made available, Advance received is on time and Long term practice is followed since their mean scores are 2.6941, 2.5523 and 2.5374 respectively. Among the ‘Other Means’ category of respondents, these factors are Storage facilities made available, Advance received is on time and Long term practice is followed since their mean scores are 2.4889, 2.3301 and 2.3253 respectively. With regard to all category of respondents, statements Immediate cash payment only has ranked the least with 2.0261, 2.1135 and 1.9388 mean scores respectively.

C. Marketing Expenses

One among the selling and distribution expenses is the expenses on marketing Tea. These cannot be avoided. But steps could be initiated to reduce them, which would result in move profit and long business. The researcher in this context felt it essential to focus on the attitude of the respondents towards marketing to middlemen.

Table 3 Attitude of Respondents towards Marketing Expenses on Tea

Sl. No	Perception	Means Score			F Statistics
		Direct Sales	Single Agent	Other Means	
1	I bear packing in gunny bags	2.4150	2.5181	2.3119	0.2450 NS
2	I bear loading	2.3203	2.4151	2.2255	3.2729*
3	I bear transport cost	2.3170	2.4152	2.2188	14.6299**
4	Unloading cost is also there	2.3595	2.4711	2.2478	1.7290 NS
5	Market fee is also there	2.1699	2.2724	2.0674	7.4662**
6	Association charge paid to traders	2.3922	2.4844	2.2992	2.6762*
7	Establishment charges reduced profit	2.6797	2.7961	2.5633	8.6273**
8	Weighing charges are also borne	2.4346	2.5415	2.3278	4.9533*
9	Traveling expenses adds loss (Collection cost)	2.2418	2.3238	2.1598	2.8055*

Source: Primary data

It is observed from Table 3 that the perception of respondents of single agent was higher in all the respects of marketing expenses except two causes than that of the respondents of direct sales and other means as revealed by the respective mean scores that are higher in the selected factors. The highly perceived factors among the respondents of ‘Direct Sales’ category are Establishment charges reduced profit, Weighing charges are also borne and I bear packing in gunny bags since their respective mean scores are 2.6796, 2.4346 and 2.4150 respectively. Among the ‘Single Agent’ category of respondents to these factors are Establishment charges reduced profit, Weighing charges are also borne and I bear packing in gunny bags since their mean scores are 2.7961, 2.5457 and 2.5181 respectively. Among the ‘Other Means’ category of respondents, these factors are Establishment charges reduced profit, Weighing charges are also borne and I bear packing in

gunny bags since their mean scores are 2.5633, 2.3278 and 2.3119 respectively. With regard to all category of respondents, statements Market fee is also there only has ranked the least with 2.1699, 2.2724 and 2.0674 mean scores respectively.

D. Marketing Cost

Cost is common on all products. It is the cost incurred after production but before sales. So many costs take place between production and sales. Most of them are direct expenses. The researcher in this context felt it essential to focus on the attitude of the respondents towards marketing to middlemen.

Table 4 Attitude of Respondents towards Marketing Cost

Sl. No	Perception	Means Score			F Statistics
		Direct Sales	Single Agent	Other Means	
1	Plucking cost in borne	2.3660	2.4643	2.2677	3.0241*
2	Loading cost is there	2.3039	2.4075	2.2003	0.2982 NS
3	Transporting cost is there	2.4314	2.5276	2.3353	0.6069 NS
4	Unloading cost is there	2.2255	2.3108	2.1402	2.9524*
5	Storage cost affects profit	2.4542	2.5665	2.3420	2.4621 NS
6	Commission charges affects profit	2.1209	2.2161	2.0257	12.632**

Source: Primary data

Table 5 Attitude of Respondents towards Marketing Cost

Sl. No	Perception	Means Score			F Statistics
		Direct Sales	Single Agent	Other Means	
1	Plucking cost in borne	2.3660	2.4643	2.2677	3.0241*
2	Loading cost is there	2.3039	2.4075	2.2003	0.2982 NS
3	Transporting cost is there	2.4314	2.5276	2.3353	0.6069 NS
4	Unloading cost is there	2.2255	2.3108	2.1402	2.9524*
5	Storage cost affects profit	2.4542	2.5665	2.3420	2.4621 NS
6	Commission charges affects profit	2.1209	2.2161	2.0257	12.632**

Source: Primary data

Table 5 shows that the perception of respondents of single agent was higher in all the respects of marketing cost except two causes than that of the respondents of direct sales and other means as revealed by the respective mean scores that are higher in the selected factors. The highly perceived factors among the respondents of 'Direct Sales' category are Storage cost affects profit, Transporting cost is there and Plucking cost in borne since their respective mean scores are 2.4542, 2.4314 and 2.3660 respectively. Among the 'Single Agent' category of respondents too these factors are Storage cost affects profit, Transporting cost is there and Plucking cost in borne since their mean scores are 2.5665, 2.5276 and 2.4643 respectively. Among the 'Other Means' category of respondents, these factors are Storage cost affects profit, Transporting cost is there and Plucking cost in borne since their mean scores are 2.3420, 2.3352 and 2.2677 respectively. With regard to

all category of respondents, statements Commission charges affects profit only has ranked the least with 2.1209, 2.2161 and 2.0257 mean scores respectively.

E. Payment

It means the money paid by the agents or middlemen to the tea manufacturers when the payment is received at the earliest, it may help the produces to do the business at case. It may not affect their working capital. The researcher in this context felt it essential to focus on the attitude of the respondents towards marketing to middlemen.

Table 6 Attitude of Respondents towards Payment

Sl. No	Perception	Means Score			F Statistics
		Direct Sales	Single Agent	Other Means	
1	Lack of prompt payment	2.3170	2.4315	2.2024	0.719 NS
2	Delay in payment	2.6667	2.7854	2.5479	1.3077 NS
3	Partial payment in sale proceeds	2.7516	2.8645	2.6388	2.2995 NS
4	Interest on crop leadings to delay in payment	2.4771	2.5846	2.3697	18.8539**
5	Marking payment on the basic of installments	2.5556	2.6523	2.4588	4.0158*

Source: Primary data

It is evident from Table 6 that the perception of respondents of direct sales was higher in all the respects of payment except two causes than that of the respondents of single agent and other means as revealed by the respective mean scores that are higher in the selected factors. The highly perceived factors among the respondents of ‘Direct Sales’ category are Partial payment in sale proceeds, Delay in payment and Marking payment on the basic of installments since their respective mean scores are 2.7516, 2.6667 and 2.5556 respectively. Among the ‘Single Agent’ category of respondents too these factors are Partial payment in sale proceeds, Delay in payment and marking payment on the basic of installments since their mean scores are 2.8645, 2.7854 and 2.6523 respectively. Among the ‘Other Means’ category of respondents, these factors are Partial payment in sale proceeds, Delay in payment and Marking payment on the basic of installments since their mean scores are 2.6388, 2.5479 and 2.4588 respectively. With regard to all category of respondents, statements ‘lack of prompt payment’ in all cases have ranked the least with 2.3170, 2.4315 and 2.2024 respectively.

Overall perception – Analysis

The overall perception represent the summation of all the perception relating to ‘marketing to middlemen’, ‘village merchants’, ‘preferring commission agents’, ‘marketing expenses on Tea’, ‘market the products immediately after harvest’, ‘marketing cost’, ‘Tea is storing’, ‘considerations in marketing process’, ‘problems associated with tea board’, ‘economic factors’, ‘finance assistance’ and ‘payment’ . The overall problem index is created by

$$OPI = W1MMI + W2PVMI + W3PCAI + W4MEI + W5MCI + W6IMPI + W7SCI + W8CMPI + W9PATB + W10EFI + W11FAI + W12PI$$

Where,

- OPI = Overall Performance Index
- MMI = Marketing to Middlemen Index
- PVMI = Preferring Village Merchants Index

- PCAI = Preferring Commission Agents Index
 MEI = Marketing Expenses Index
 MCI = Marketing Cost Index
 IMPI = Market the Products Immediately after Harvest Index
 SCI = Storage of Commodities Index
 CMPI = Considerations in Marketing Process Index
 PATB = Problem Associated with Tea Board Index
 EFI = Economic Factors Index
 FAI = Financial Assistance Index
 PI = Payments Index
 W1, W2, W3, W4, W5, W6, W7,
 W8, W9, W10, W11, W12 = Weightage of the above said indices

$$W1 = \frac{\sum MSAMMV}{\sum MSAMMV + \sum MSAPVMV + \sum MSAPCAV + \sum MSAMEV + \sum MSAMCV + \sum MSAIMPV + \sum MSASCV + \sum MSACMPV + \sum MSAPATBV + \sum MSAEFV + \sum MSAFAV + \sum MSAPV}$$

Where,

- MSAMMV = Maximum Score in the Attitude towards Marketing to Middlemen
 MSAPVMV = Maximum Score in the Attitude towards Preferring Village Merchants Variable
 MSAPCAV = Maximum Score in the Attitude towards Preferring Commission Agents Variable
 MSAMEV = Maximum Score in the Attitude towards Marketing Expenses Variable
 MSAMCV = Maximum Score in the Attitude towards Marketing Cost Variable
 MSAIMPV = Maximum Score in the Attitude towards Market the Products Immediately after Harvest Variable
 MSASCV = Maximum Score in the Attitude towards Storage of Commodities Variable
 MSACMPV = Maximum Score in the Attitude towards Considerations in Marketing Process Variable
 MSAPATBV = Maximum Score in the Attitude towards Problem Associated with Tea Board Variable
 MSAEFV = Maximum Score in the Attitude towards Economic Factors Variable
 MSAFAV = Maximum Score in the Attitude towards Financial Assistance Variable
 MSAPV = Maximum Score in the Attitude towards Payments Variable

Likewise W2, W3, W4, W5, W6, W7, W8, W9, W10, W11 and W12 were found out.

The Overall Perception Index (OPI) of the respondents is computed. The OPI among the respondents is confined to 25-50 per cent and 50- 75 per cent. The distribution of respondents according to OPI is shown in Table 5.25.

Table 7 Overall Perception Index (OPI) among Respondents

Sl. No	OPI in Percentage	Number of Respondents			Total
		Direct Sales	Single Agent	Other Means	
1	25-50	92 (26.3)	71 (20.3)	79 (22.6)	242 (69.1)
2	50-75	48 (13.7)	39 (11.1)	21 (6.0)	108 (30.9)
	Total	140 (40.0)	110 (31.4)	100 (28.6)	350 (100)

Source : Computed data

Figures in parentheses denote percentages to total

Table 7 clearly shows that, in total, a maximum of 69.1 per cent of the respondents had OPI of 25-50 per cent and 30.9 per cent of the respondents had OPI of 50-75 per cent. The number of respondents of direct sales having OPI of 25-50 per cent constituted 26.3 per cent of its total' whereas respondents of single agent having OPI of 25-50 per cent constituted 20.3 per cent. In the case of other means the number of respondents having OPI of 25-50 per cent constituted 22.6 per cent of its total. At the same time, respondents of direct sales having OPI of 50-75 per cent constituted 13.7 per cent of its total and the respondents of single agent having OPI of 50-75 per cent constituted 11.1 per cent. In the case of other means it was 6.0 per cent.

From the foregoing analysis it may be inferred that 69.1 per cent of the respondents were came under than 50 per cent of the OP index. It implies that over all perception in the study area to the respondents is satisfactory and there is a good scope for further development of business in the study area.

Findings

The following are the findings of the study:

1. Perception of all the three category respondents is positive towards the attitude in Marketing to Middlemen. It implies that the perception to marketing to middlemen prevailing in the study area is below average and it is a good sign for further development.
2. The respondents of all the three category of respondents towards the attitude in preferring village agents. Preferring village merchants prevailing in the study area is below average.
3. The attitude in marketing expenses on Tea. It implies that the perception to marketing expenses on Tea prevailing in the study area is below average and it is a good sign for further development.
4. The perception to marketing cost prevailing in the study area is below average and it is a good sign for further development.
5. The perception to storing of commodities prevailing in the study area is below average and it is a good sign for further development.
6. The perception of the respondents of all the three category of respondents is positive towards the attitude in consideration in marketing process. It implies that the perception to considerations in the process of marketing prevailing in the study area is below average.
7. Perception on the problems associated with the tea board prevailing in the study area is below average and it is a good sign for further development.

8. The overall analysis clearly reveals that the perception of the respondents of all the three category of respondents is positive towards the attitude in financial assistance. It implies that the perception to financial assistance prevailing in the study area is below average and it is a good sign for further development.
9. The analysis it may be inferred that 69.1 per cent of the respondents came under less than 50 per cent of the OP index. It implies that over all perception in the study area to the respondents is satisfactory and there is a good scope for further development of business in the study area.

Suggestions

Based on the findings of the study the following suggestions are made

- a) Vital information on marketing viz, price, market and export may be passed to the growers and traders through the media and other means communication.
- b) Most of the forest area like remote place, we have provide all facilities like transportation, price and commission level meetings to be conducted the growers and traders.
- c) Tamil Nadu government helps to provide agricultural clinic to the growers about medicinal uses of tea cultivation.
- d) The cultivators should be advised to bring their produce, after removing over mature and unhealthy tea leaves to the market so that they can get reasonal price for their product.
- e) The agricultural department helps to provide sibling of Tea to the formers.
- f) The agricultural department most create the awareness of organic farming and benefits to tea growers and they provide bio pest control technology information to the farmers.
- g) Liberal financial assistance to the tea cultivators such as crop loan development loans for meeting, irrigation facilities, bank and primary agricultural and rural development bank can be provided.
- h) The ministry of agricultural department of Tamil Nadu can like with action centre provide realiable data to the cultivators in same manner.
- i) Electronic auction system as introduced by tea board is good but it has to be made foot proof. The flaws in electronic system needs to be rectified and to be made user friendly.
- j) New products like iced tea, herbal tea, may be promoted to increase penetration in the market. Technology to be made available for flavoured tea.
- k) Exhibitions, workshops etc to be organized to promote Nilgiris tea in the domestic and international markets.
- l) Tamil Nadu government may take steps to curb adulteration of tea. Quality to be maintained for both domestic and international markets.

Conclusion

Nowadays the habit of consuming Tea by people of every category has become a common feature. So the government has to extend its help to the Tea producers in respect of price, fixation and grading subsidies. The government can take earnest steps to provide more infrastructure facilities to the Tea producers. Good manure and latest weeding machines can also be supplied to the producers so as to reduce the cost of production and enhance the standard of living of the tea producers.

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